

Trust, resources, and publication culture Groups of editors and their willingness to embrace technical innovations

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Introduction

The University Library of Bern conducted a survey of journal editors for the third part of its CRAFT-OA reports¹. The survey participants included attendees of the second CRAFT-OA Summer School and editors of Swiss Diamond Open Access journals.

The aim of the survey was to refine the findings on the acceptance of technologies and tools obtained in the second part of UB Bern's CRAFT-OA reports² and make them usable for subsequent CRAFT-OA projects.

Although the number of responses to the survey may not be representative, the results of the survey do provide an overview of the groups of editors that National Capacity Centers can expect to encounter in terms of their ability and willingness to accept technical innovations. This will allow conclusions to be drawn about the type of information, training, and services that can be used to reach these groups.

The survey

The second CRAFT-OA Summer School for journal editors took place from June 23 to 27, 2025, in Coimbra, Portugal. The topics covered at the Summer School included:

- Setting up a journal in OJS + editorial workflow
- OJS core feature enhancements
- Peer review in OJS
- XML publishing
- Full text HTML publishing with OJS based on JATS-XML
- Aggregators and their requirements: OpenAlex, DOAJ, OpenAire
- Coping with aggregator requirements / Indexes Knowledge Base
- OJS Diamond Plug-ins³

The participating editors of the summer school had time to complete the survey during the summer school from June 23 to 27, 2025. Of the 52 registered participants, 26 took part in the survey. The survey was conducted online using Ilias.⁴

The summer school program, with its strong focus on the OJS publication software and XML and HTML publication formats, leads to the conclusion that this group consists of editors with above-average technical interest and expertise. The following results also underline this group's openness to new technical solutions.

¹ Pellin, Elio, & Verdicchio, Dirk (2024a). Interviews for CRAFT-OA. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11654584>

Strub, Laura; Pellin, Elio; Verdicchio, Dirk (2025). A complex social and cultural process. Acceptance of new tools and technologies in OA publishing.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17798564>

² Strub, Laura; Pellin, Elio; Verdicchio, Dirk (2025). A complex social and cultural process. Acceptance of new tools and technologies in OA publishing.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17798564>

³ Detailed program of the summer school in the appendix.

⁴ Questionnaire in the appendix

For comparison and as a supplement, a second group was surveyed. Swiss open access journals from the Plato project address list⁵ were contacted. The invitation to participate in the survey went to 320 addresses. The heterogeneity of this group of journals is more representative of the Diamond landscape than the group of summer school participants – not only for Switzerland, but also for other countries in Europe. The results of the entire survey (both parts) allow groups of editors to be identified – depending on their willingness to accept new technical solutions. This is of particular, but not exclusive, interest for the orientation and development of the Swiss National Capacity Center.⁶

Of the more than 300 editorial teams contacted, 75 participated in the survey between June 10 and July 7, 2025. The title and description of the survey were designed to attract participation primarily from those editors who are open to improvements in principle.

Technical Improvement for Swiss OA Journals

The OJS Swiss Community of Practice aims to improve the conditions for Diamond OA publishing in Switzerland. We would like to know how you use and implement the tools available to you. If you take a few minutes to answer our five questions, it will help us make OA publishing in Switzerland easier.

However, the answers to the questions on publication formats (questions 3 and 4) show that the possibilities for using technical tools may be limited for journals in this group. No fewer than 11 out of 50 respondents agree (6) or slightly agree (5) that there is no one in their editorial team who is interested in technical issues such as the production of HTMLs. When asked about XMLs, the figure is 10 (7 / 3) out of 49.

⁵ Plato (Platinum Open Access Funding) ran from January 2022 to December 2024. Project partners were the University of Zurich, the University of Bern, the University of Geneva, the University of Neuchâtel, Zurich University of the Arts, ETH Zurich, and the Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences (SAGW). (Project results: <https://zenodo.org/communities/plato-ch>)

⁶ The OJS Swiss Community of Practice, which connects the IPSPs of Swiss universities, is working on DOACH a project supported by swissuniversities to establish a single point of access for diamond publishing in Switzerland: www.diamondopenaccess.ch

Results

Trust in the publication software

15 editors from the summer school responded to the second question:

Change in the use of the publishing system

Your publication system (e.g., OJS) is continuously being improved and expanded. Can you see yourself using more of the system's functionalities in the future?

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

All agreed with the first statement on this question:

1. Yes, we would like to optimize our processes with the possibilities of the system.

Figure 1

Of the editors of Swiss journals, 53 answered the question. 42 of them (79.25%) also agreed (28) or slightly agreed (14) with statement 1.

Figure 2

The willingness to accept improvements, changes, and new possibilities offered by the publication software is very high in both groups. However, the desire to optimize publication processes can conflict with the need for stable and established processes. Of the 20 editors of Swiss journals who stated in the second question that they do not want to use more of the system's functionalities in the future because their editorial processes are well established and should not be changed (3rd answer: 5/15), 12 nevertheless stated that they would like to optimize their process with the possibilities offered by the system (1st answer: 4/8). It can be concluded from this that they want or hope for improvements through the system that leave their editorial processes unchanged. The less a technical innovation changes established routines and processes, the greater its acceptance.

Of the 15 editors from the summer school who answered the first question, 13 rejected the third answer (12/1) that their editorial processes were well established and they did not want to change anything. This group is clearly willing to accept technical innovations that also change the editorial process. Of these 13, 11 also stated that they use the publication system for submissions and the peer review process because it is practical for them (question 1, answer 1). They clearly consider this functionality of the system to be an advantage and are willing to adapt their working methods accordingly.

14 editors from the summer school answered the fifth question:

The new DISCO Plugin

There is a new plug-in for OJS that helps with journal indexing. The plug-in provides a whole series of checkboxes that you can work through. At the end, it displays whether your journal meets the requirements of various indexes. Will you consider installing the new DISCO plug-in?

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

All agreed (13) or slightly agreed (1) with the third statement on this question.

3. Yes, we are always open to using new OJS features that improve the editorial processes.

Figure 3

46 editors of Swiss journals answered the fifth question. 35 of them (75.09%) also agreed (26) or slightly agreed (9) with the third statement.⁷

Figure 4

The vast majority of respondents welcome or even expect improvements to the editorial work through enhancements to the publication system and its extensions. The acceptance of technical innovations is high among editors who express "a clear need for reliability, manageable processes, and a familiar working environment" (Strub et al., 2025, p. 13) in a system that has been experienced as reliable over the years. In this case, technical innovations are not seen as a potential risk to stability but can be integrated into established and accepted structures. The resulting willingness to use new system features and new plugins demonstrates a remarkable level of trust in the publication system on the one hand, and on the other hand in the community that supports and develops the open-source system and its extensions. This confirms the statement in *A complex social and cultural process* that new tools are more likely to be accepted "if they come from the 'right' provider – for example, from an association that shares the same values with regard to open access and can therefore be trusted to a certain extent." (Strub et al., 2025, p. 13)

⁷ The figures here differ slightly from those in the DIAMAS gap analysis: 42% say they are already well indexed, while 51% would like to see technical optimizations for better indexing (Brun, V., Torny, D., & Pontille, D. (2023). D3.3 Report on the gap analysis results_Under EC review (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10083615>p. 50).

Willingness to optimize

The two surveyed groups differ in their willingness to use features of the publication system.

To the first question

Do you use your publishing system (for example OJS) for the submission or review process?

17 participants in the summer school responded.

The first answer (Yes, that's practical for us) was agreed with by 70.59% (11) or slightly agreed with (1).

64.7% agreed (10) or slightly agreed (1) with the second answer (Yes, that is a requirement that we have to meet).

17.64% stated that they prefer personal email to the workflow via the system (2/1).

Figure 5

Of the 54 editors of Swiss journals, 55.55% agreed with the first answer to this question (22/8).

Only 29.63% agreed with answer 2 (13/3).

A much larger proportion than among the Summer School participants (55.55%) stated that they preferred personal email (17/13). And another 24.07% agreed (8) or slightly agreed (5) with the fourth answer (No, it is too complicated). Among the summer school participants, only one partially agreed with the answer No, it's too complicated.

Only a few editorial teams use an external tool for the submission and review process.

Figure 6

Of the 30 editors of Swiss journals who stated that they work with personal emails, 12 (8 / 4) agreed or slightly agreed with the fourth answer (too complicated).

Twenty-two of these 30 agreed with the first answer (Yes, we would like to optimize our processes with the possibilities of the system) to the second question (14/8). Of the 12 editorial teams that find the submission and peer review process via the system too complicated, 10 (6/4) state that they want to optimize their editorial processes with the possibilities offered by the system.

These editorial teams are therefore open to the possibilities of the publication system, but do not see any potential for optimization in the submission and review process within the system for their editorial office.

Optimization is often not assessed solely on the basis of functional criteria.

Respondents perceive technology not only as a neutral tool, but as part of their editorial identity and work culture. Editors emphasize that the way they organize or communicate information is closely linked to their editorial role and their self-image as a responsible authority (Strub et al., 2025, p. 14).

Direct email contact with authors and reviewers is often part of well-established routines (cf. Strub et al., 2025, p. 15) and an essential component of the editorial self-image. Regardless of technical functionality, it is seen as an advantage over a (partially) automated workflow via the system.

New tools or features become attractive when they are practical, i.e., require as little effort as possible and are easy to use, and when they relate to areas of publishing that are considered important. This is evident in the question about the new OJS plugin DISCO.

Fourteen participants in the summer school responded to the question about the DISCO plugin (fifth question). Twelve agreed with the first answer (Yes, it will make indexing easier for us) (11) or slightly agreed (1). Another 12 agreed with the second answer (Yes, because indexing is central for us) (11) or slightly agreed (1). See Fig. 3

Of the 46 editors of Swiss journals who answered the fifth question, 71.74% (24/9) believe that the DISCO plugin is of interest to them because it makes indexing easier. 69.46% (21/11) are

considering the plugin because indexing is central to their work. 26.08% (1/11) suspect that the effort required to use the plugin is too great for them. See Fig. 4

Resources, effort

It is not surprising that resources play a role when it comes to optimizing publication processes. Of the 14 editors of Swiss journals who answered the second question by saying that changes to the process would exceed their capacities (4th answer: 7/7), 12 stated that they would still like to optimize their processes using the system's capabilities (6/6). This group would be dependent on improvements to the system that do not exceed their capabilities in terms of initial effort or operation.

A similar pattern can be observed with regard to publication format. Twenty-one editors of Swiss journals agreed (11) or slightly agreed (10) with the seventh answer (We do not produce HTMLs. We have no resources to produce them) to the third question (Does your journal publish articles as HTMLs?). Of this group, 9 stated that they would like to produce HTMLs and are looking for a good conversion tool (2nd answer). A "good tool," as can be concluded from this group, is a tool that does not require additional resources and can be operated within the existing editorial workload.

Identity and work culture

19 of the editors of Swiss journals state that they do not publish HTML versions of their articles because PDF is still the best format (3rd question, 5th answer, 9/10).⁸ The fact that this group does not have a fundamentally low level of technology acceptance is demonstrated by the fact that 15 of these 19 would like to optimize their editorial processes with the capabilities of the publication system (2nd question, 1st answer, 10/5). And 13 of these 19 can imagine using the DISCO plugin because they are always open to new OJS features that improve the publication process (5th question, 3rd answer; 10/3).

This group's adherence to PDF as a publication format is therefore not an expression of fundamental reluctance toward technical innovations and the uncertainties associated with them, but rather a preservation of editorial identity and work culture. This also includes the publication culture in which a journal is located, a culture with certain customs in the respective areas of scientific publishing and with a tradition of publication formats. While changing the publication format is seen as a change in editorial identity and work culture, a new OJS plugin such as DISCO is seen as a support in fulfilling an important task: 12 (10 / 2) of these 19 state that they would use the plugin because indexing is central to them (question 5, answer 1).

The system (in most cases OJS) is recognized as reliable and part of the operating culture, part of the familiar working environment, and acceptance of changes and improvements to the system is correspondingly high.

Training and practice

Of the 23 editors of Swiss journals who stated that they would like to make better use of the system's functionalities in the future but that good training material is lacking (question 2, answer 2, 9/14), 18 (11/7) stated that they use the system for the submission or review process

⁸ The *Report on the gap analysis report* (Brun et al. 2023) had stated the following regarding the continued use of PDF as a publication format: "Either they consider it a bad format but have no choice, or they believe that readers, authors, and editors are fine with it." The results of our survey of Swiss journals confirm these two groups, which are of similar size. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10083615>

because it is convenient for them (question 1, 1st answer). This is a group that is highly accepting of the system's technical solutions and believes that better training materials would further optimize the system. Twelve (5/7) of this group state that they do not have the resources to create HTMLs (3rd question, 7th answer). So here we are dealing with a group that shows a high level of acceptance for the technical capabilities of the system but is looking for training and education opportunities that enable optimization with few resources, i.e., with little additional time expenditure. While the participants in the summer school in Portugal are editors not only with a keen interest in technical improvements but also with access to sufficient resources to travel for several days for further training, these editors are equally interested in technology and likely to be receptive to less time-consuming offerings.

Of the summer school participants, 8 out of 15 agreed (1) or slightly agreed (7) that there is a lack of good training material. Apparently, even among the group of editors who cannot be reached with low-threshold training courses, there is a need for better training material for the publication system.

Conclusions

Based on the results of this survey, in conjunction with the findings of *A complex social and cultural process*. (Strub et al., 2025), it is possible to outline several groups according to their motivations for accepting technical innovations. These groups, or rather the conditions under which they accept technical improvements, are of interest to the Swiss National Capacity Center DOACH⁹, but also to other NCCs and the EDCH. They provide clues for the targeted design and adaptation of training materials, information, and services.

System and workflows

In general, it can be said that the respondents have a high level of trust in the publication system and that the acceptance of technical innovations within the publication software is greater than of technical innovations outside the system.

Here we can identify three groups:

- **Workflow:** willing to change workflows in favor of technical innovations.
- **System:** welcomes innovations introduced by the system, but there is little or no willingness to change work processes. As *A complex social and cultural process* notes, this reluctance can be a "conscious strategy to limit uncertainty and ensure continuity" (Strub et al., 2025, p. 14).
- **Training:** interested in changes/improvements but better training materials are desired.

Training

The group that shows great interest in technical innovations but would like better training materials can be divided into two subgroups:

- **Training extended:** People are willing to undergo extensive training (e.g., time and travel budget) in order to learn about technical innovations.
- **Training in brief:** They want training but are dependent on a less extensive training program.

⁹ www.diamondopenaccess.ch

Effort

- **Resources easy:** Innovations must not be too complicated and must be easy to implement. A majority of this group states that there is no one in their editorial office who is interested in technical solutions/innovations. For this group, particular emphasis must also be placed on the comprehensibility of terminology (Strub et al., p. 16f.). Uncertainty about terminology leads to lower acceptance of technical innovations.
- **Resources equal:** Technical innovations are welcome. The resources required for setup and operation must not exceed the existing editorial effort. This group relies on information – such as the experiences of others from trial operations – about the effort involved in operating the new technical offering. (Strub et al., p. 14)
- **Resources plus:** When the benefits of a technical innovation are recognized, the resources for its introduction and operation are provided. This group is most likely to include editors/journals that test new technical offerings and share their findings with less resource-rich or more cautious editorial teams (Strub et al., 2025, p. 14).

Operating culture and self-image

Publishing culture: This group accepts technical innovations if they are considered essential for editorial tasks and are compatible with the operating culture and self-image of the journal. For this group, it is important that IPSPs and NCCs are close to editorial teams and research communities.

In particular, technical innovations for this group must not be designed in such a way that they are perceived as black boxes and thus associated with a possible loss of transparency and active decision-making authority. (Strub et al., 2025, p. 15, p.18)

References

Brun, V., Torny, D., & Pontille, D. (2023). D3.3 Report on the gap analysis results_Under EC review. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10083615>

Strub, Laura; Pellin, Elio; Verdicchio, Dirk: A complex social and cultural process. Acceptance of new tools and technologies in OA publishing, 2025.

Appendices

Publishing System

Do you use your publishing system (for example OJS) for the submission or review process?

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

*

	disagree	slightly disagree	slightly agree	agree	no answer
Yes, that's practical for us.	<input type="radio"/>				
Yes, that is a requirement that we have to meet.	<input type="radio"/>				
No, we prefer personal e-mails.	<input type="radio"/>				
No, it is too complicated.	<input type="radio"/>				
No, we use an external tool.	<input type="radio"/>				

*Erforderliche Angabe

Change in the use of the publishing system

Your publication system (e.g., OJS) is continuously being improved and expanded. Can you see yourself using more of the system's functionalities in the future?

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

*

	disagree	slightly disagree	slightly agree	agree	no answer
Yes, we would like to optimize our processes with the possibilities of the system.	<input type="radio"/>				
Yes, but good training and information are not available.	<input type="radio"/>				
No, our processes are well established, we don't want to change anything.	<input type="radio"/>				
No, changing our processes exceeds our capacities.	<input type="radio"/>				
No, such suggestions only ever lead to unproductive discussions in our editorial board.	<input type="radio"/>				

*Erforderliche Angabe

Publication formats: HTMLs

Does your journal publish articles as HTMLs?

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

*

	disagree	slightly disagree	slightly agree	agree	no answer
We already produce HTMLs and are interested in learning about new tools for file-conversion. <input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
We would like to create HTML formats and have been searching for a good conversion tool for some time. <input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
We do not think that's necessary. <input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
We do not produce HTMLs. We don't have anyone in the editorial board who is interested in these technical topics. <input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
We do not produce HTMLs. PDF is still the best format. <input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
We do not produce HTMLs. Our authors want only PDFs. <input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
We do not produce HTMLs. We have no resources to produce them. <input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

*Erforderliche Angabe

Publication formats: XML

Do you provide XMLs of the articles in your journal / on your platform?

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

*

	disagree	slightly disagree	slightly agree	agree	no answer
We already produce XMLs and are interested in learning about new tools for file-conversion.	<input type="radio"/>				
We would like to create XML formats and have been searching for a good conversion tool for some time.	<input type="radio"/>				
We do not think that's necessary.	<input type="radio"/>				
We do not produce XMLs. We don't have anyone in the editorial board who is interested in these technical topics.	<input type="radio"/>				
We do not produce XMLs. PDF is still the best format.	<input type="radio"/>				
We do not produce XMLs. Our authors are not interested in XMLs.	<input type="radio"/>				
We do not produce XMLs. We have no resources to produce them.	<input type="radio"/>				

*Erforderliche Angabe

The new DISCO Plugin

There is a new plug-in for OJS that helps with journal indexing. The plug-in provides a whole series of checkboxes that you can work through. At the end, it displays whether your journal meets the requirements of various indexes. Will you consider installing the new DISCO plug-in?

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

*

	disagree	slightly disagree	slightly agree	agree	no answer
Yes, it will make indexing easier for us. <input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Yes, because indexing is central for us. <input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Yes, we are always open to using new OJS features that improve the editorial processes. <input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
No, indexing is not important for us. <input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
No, we are in all the indexes that are important to us. <input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
No, we cannot implement the plugin ourselves. <input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
No, the effort to use the plug-in is / could be too big. <input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

*Erforderliche Angabe

	2nd CRAFT-OA Summer School for Journal Editors							
	PROGRAMME							
	<i>(might be subject to last minute change)</i>							
Monday 23 June								
9.30–9.45	Welcome & Introduction (UC & CRAFT-OA representatives)							
9.45–10.30	Main outcomes from DIAMAS & CRAFT-OA (Martina Dvořáková)							
10.30–11.00	Coffee break							
11.00–12.00	What's new in PKP/OJS (Dulip Whithanage)							
12.00–13.00	The Mondaecus Translation Service (Delfim Leao)							
13.00–14.00	Lunch							
14.00–15.00	OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard (Leonidas Pispiringas)							
15.00–15.30	Coffee break							
15.30–16.30	Setting up a journal in OJS + Editorial workflow (Radek Gomola)							
16.30–17.30	Journals/Platforms/Projects poster session							
18.30	Conference dinner							
Tuesday 24 June								
9.30–11.00	OJS Core feature enhancements (Antti-Jussi Nygard, Dulip Whithanage)							
11.00–11.30	Coffee break							
11.30–13.00	Peer-review in OJS (Mickael Gomes de Silva)							
13.00–14.00	Lunch							
14.00–15.30	OJS Themes (Radek Gomola)				OR 15.00–16.30	University of Coimbra Campus guided tour		
15.30–16.00	Coffee break							
16.00–17.30	Beyond the everyday (group discussion)							
Wednesday 25 June								
9.30–11.00	XML Publishing I (Maxim Kupreyev)							
11.00–11.30	Coffee break							
11.30–13.00	XML publishing II (Dulip Withanage)							
13.00–14.00	Lunch							
14.00–15.30	Full-text HTML publishing with OJS based on JATS-XML (Gennaro Razzi)							
15.30–16.00	Coffee break							
16.00–17.30	Aggregators and their requirements: OpenAlex, DOAJ, OpenAIRE							
Thursday 26 June								
9.30–11.00	Coping with aggregators requirements / Indexes Knowledge Base (Arnaud Gingold)							
11.00–11.30	Coffee break							
11.30–13.00	Metadata enhancing + Bibliometrics, Altmetrics & other CrossRef tools (Radek Gomola)							
13.00–14.00	Lunch							
14.00–15.30	OJS Diamond Plugins (Martina Dvořáková, Radek Gomola)							
15.30–17.30	Coimbra City Tour							
Friday 27 June								
9.30–10.30	Diamond Open Access Standard – DOAS (Virginia de Pablo Llorente)							
10.30–11.00	Coffee break							
11.00–12.30	Institutional Publishing Technical Living Handbook (Isabella Greiner)							
12.00–13.00	Diamond Discovery Hub (Hanna Varachkina)							
13.00–14.00	Lunch							
14.00–15.00	Beyond CRAFT-OA: The European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) (Marion Paulhac)							
15.00–15.30	Wrap up & Goodbye							
For more information please follow www.craft-oa.eu or contact Aminata Keita (ami.keita@press.muni.cz)								